

ABSTRACT BOOK

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"DATA-DRIVEN ENVIRONMENTAL DECISION-MAKING"

the water hardness simultaneously, and that Shapley values are a versatile and useful alternative for gene ranking, providing insight into the importance of individual genes.

1.05.P Epigenetic Changes Modulating the Response of Organisms to Environmental Challenges: From Phenotypic Effects to Microevolution Patterns

1.05.P-Th012 Incorporating Epigenetics in Adverse Outcome Pathways: The EPIBOOST Project

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Lately, environmental studies started appraising several 'omics, e.g., epigenomics, as remarkable tools to improve Ecological Risk Assessment (ERA) frameworks. Besides the mechanistic enlightening of toxicity that these 'omics can provide in general, the discovery of molecular initiating events and molecular pathways for adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) is promoted. While epigenetic modifications are likely primary molecular initiating events as per their role in constraining gene expression, there are still important challenges to overcome in order to incorporate epigenomics into regulatory frameworks, especially because consistent links to effects at the level of the phenotype (and then to higher levels of biological organization for improved ecological relevance) are yet to be established, as well as are trends and parallels across species. This is the foundation of the EPIBOOST research, a project addressing environmental epigenetics concerning aquatic organisms and model pollutants. EPIBOOST will focus on AOPs initiated by DNA methylation in model freshwater and marine organisms (microalgae, microcrustaceans, and fish), exposed to three model chemicals representing persistent or emerging threats nowadays or in the near future (metals, antibiotics, and toxins). Briefly, samples will be screened for global methylation and analysed via whole-genome bisulfite sequencing. Gene expression will be assessed via targeted or untargeted approaches to understand whether gene expression correlates to the changes in the epigenome. Phenotypic effects ranging from the subcellular to the population level will be assessed in parallel concerning specific (e.g., photosynthetic efficiency, neurotoxicity) and more general (e.g., growth rates, behaviour) responses to stress. Such a comprehensive approach will allow a meaningful insight on the AOPs for the selected model contaminants in the aquatic compartment, and particularly support the validation of epigenetic modifications as robust molecular initiating events.

1.05.P-Th013 Time- and Dose-Dependent DNA Methylation Changes in Earthworms Exposed to Cadmium: Genome Wide and Gene-Specific Epigenetic Perspective

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The heavy metal cadmium (Cd) can cause DNA hypermethylation, which has already been demonstrated in many invertebrates, including earthworms. However, detailed characterisation of DNA methylation landscape upon Cd exposure, as well as mechanisms behind the DNA hypermethylation, are still largely unexplored. Therefore, in this study, we used the earthworm model *Lumbricus terrestris* to explore time- and dose-dependent effects of Cd on global, genome wide, and gene-specific DNA methylation and its underlying mechanisms. Earthworms were exposed to two Cd concentrations (10 and 25 mg/kg) for a period of 12 weeks and sampled at several time points (1, 2, 4, 12 weeks). Global cytosine hypermethylation was revealed using specific antibodies in dot blots, whereas bsRADseq was used to determine genome wide DNA methylation changes and pinpoint specific genomic regions mostly affected by Cd exposure. To study the underlying mechanisms, we determined the gene expression as well as the activity of DNA methylation and demethylation components like DNA methyltransferases (DNMT1 and 3), and ten-eleven translocation (TET) genes. However, neither gene expression nor DNMT and TET enzyme activity showed significant differences in the Cd exposure groups. More specifically, we focused on the gene body methylation (gbm) of metallothionein 2 (MT2), one of the most important Cd detoxification proteins. Using bisulfite conversion and sequencing we were able to detect some changes in MT2 gbm; however, these changes could not be correlated to MT2 gene expression. The results of this study demonstrate the importance of studying epigenetic marks and underlying mechanisms in organisms under pollution pressure and point to missing links, which need to be further explored.

1.05.P-Th014 Multigenerational DNA Methylation Patterns Following Copper Exposure in *Daphnia*: The Role of Exposure History

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Epigenetic mechanisms are moving to the forefront of environmental sciences because of their key role in shaping gene-environment interactions, phenotypic plasticity, and evolutionary responses. Specifically, environmentally induced DNA methylation changes are known to shape biological responses to chemical contamination, and the transgenerational inheritance of methylation marks across nonexposed generations has been confirmed in invertebrate and vertebrate species. Here, we focused on the freshwater invertebrate *Daphnia magna*, with the goal of further understanding the involvement of DNA methylation in their response and eventual adaptation to copper contamination. To do so, we specifically tested the hypothesis that different histories

Incorporating epigenetics in Adverse Outcome Pathways

The EPIBOOST project

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CONTEXT

- *Omics* can assist the discovery of molecular initiating events (MIE) and **adverse outcome pathways (AOPs)**.
- **Epigenetic modifications** are likely primary MIE as per their role in constraining **gene expression**.
- The incorporation of epigenomics into regulatory frameworks through AOP refining is challenging as consistent links to effects at the level of the phenotype are yet largely to be established, as well as are trends and parallels across species.
- EPIBOOST will focus on **DNA methylation changes** in model **freshwater and marine organisms** (microalgae, microcrustaceans and fish) exposed to three model chemicals that represent persistent or emerging threats nowadays or in the near future (**metals, PPCPs and toxins**).
- The experimental approach will allow a meaningful insight on the AOPs for the selected model contaminants in the aquatic compartment, and particularly support the validation of epigenetic modifications as robust molecular initiating events, transferable across species, within and between environmental compartments.

EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

EPIBOOST OVERVIEW

- Twinning project, coordinated by an Institution in a Widening country (University of Aveiro) and having CSIC and the University of Ghent as Advanced partners supporting the leveraging of excellence in environmental epigenetics.
- Essentially a capacitation project focused on training towards excellence, concerning **research**, but also science management and administration.
- Entails a research project: **Responses of model organisms to relevant environmental contaminants**.

EXPECTED SCIENTIFIC OUTPUTS

- Increased knowledge of AOPs for the model contaminants in the aquatic compartment, through an understanding of the relationships between phenotypic effects following exposure, with methylation patterns and gene expression.
- Epigenetic alterations supported as reliable molecular initiating events.
- Insights on the stability of stressor-driven epigenetic changes between species of the same group inhabiting different environmental compartments.
- Insights on the stressor-specificity of epigenetic changes across different species and groups of organisms.

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